

An Empirical study of Turnover Intentions in Commercial Banking Sector

¹Dr. M. Muthukumaran & ²Dr.K.Lavanyalatha

¹Assistant Professor, Centre for Applied Research, Gandhigram Rural Institute, Gandhigram, Dindugal, Tamil Nadu (India)

²Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies, Pondicherry University, Pondicherry (India)

ARTICLE DETAILS

Article History

Published Online: 09 March 2019

Keywords

Turnover intention, job stress, organizational justice, organizational commitment

*Corresponding Author

Email: muthudvp[at]yahoo.co.in

Klavanyalatha[at]gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study attempts to assess the relationships among job stress, organizational justice, organizational commitment and turnover intentions of bank employees. Data were collected using a stratified random sampling technique from 221 employees working at public and private sector banks in Tamilnadu. A well-structured scale was used for the primary data collection. To analyze and interpret the relationships among the variables, this study adopted descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analyses. The study found that job stress has significant positive relation with turnover intention. Organizational justice and organizational commitment has significant negative relationship with turnover intention.

1. Introduction

Organizations cannot succeed without its human capital. Recruiting a best talent is more important to the organizations, more than that retaining the talented employees is very crucial because of the dynamism of the human resources. In this highly competitive job market it is really critical in attracting talents competed with the business rivalries. In this juncture employee turnover acts as a giant which is difficult to manage to the human resource managers. There is no proper framework for turnover intention to understand as whole, a list of factors have been identified to address this employee's quit (Kevin, Joan & Adrian, 2004). The Indian banking sector also faces the same issue due to various issues like poor training and development, poor ergonomics, conflict, lack of managerial skill and etc., (Shukla & Sinha 2013). The study is aimed to find out the reasons behind the issue of turnover intent.

2. Literature review

2.1 Turnover intention

Employee turnover is the ration between the number of employees left and number of employees in the particular organization during a particular period (Price, 1977). It is referred as the amount of movement of the employees from one organization which is normally depicted in turnover ratio (Chruden& Sherman, 1972).Mobley (1982) defined employee turnover takes place when an employee breaching his membership from one organization.

2.2 Job stress

Increasing amount of economic interdependence between the countries because of globalized working culture, development of technology have change the working culture in few decades and that lead to job pressure, high demand of work, role conflicts, insufficient working conditions and dynamic customers are cause stress on bank employees. (Giga &Hoel, 2003 as cited in Shukla & Sinha (2013). This pressure tend to job related stress, and followed by poor commitment, low job

satisfaction make employees to leave their working places (Firth et al., 2004).

2.3 Organizational justice

According to Aryee, Budhwar, & Chen (2002) Organizational justice is "the individual's and the group's perception of the fairness of treatment received from an organization and their behavioral reaction to such perceptions". It is a multidimensional context which includes distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice (Cohen-Charash& Spector, 2001). The literature is established strong evidences on employee's injustice perception may affect their job dissatisfaction, poor commitment, low performance and leads high intention to quit their job (Dailey & Kirk, 1992; Earley& Lind, 1987; Cohen-Charsh& Spector, 2001;Naumann& Bennett, 2002).

2.4 Organizational commitment

Organizational commitment is degree of an employee's identification with their organization (Mowday, Steers, & Porter, 1979). It is characterized by a strong belief in accepting the organization's goals and values, willingness to show adequate effort for the organization, and willing to retain the organizational membership by the employees (Mowday, Steers, & Porter, 1979).Meyer and Allen (1991) defined commitment is a psychological state which an employee has a desire, a need, and an obligation to maintain his/her employment in an organization.

3. Conceptual Model

The conceptual model is prepared with the aim of assessing the role of stress, organizational justice and organizational commitment in predicting turnover intentions. Figure 1 is showing the conceptual model of the present study.

4. Objectives

1. To explore the major reasons for employee turnover in banking sector.
2. To find out the relationship between employee turnover and the three variables namely job stress, organizational justice, and organizational commitment.

5. Methodology

The study is empirical in nature. In this turnover intention is the dependent variable, and job stress, organizational justice and organizational commitment are chosen as independent variables. Both primary and secondary data are used for the study. Primary data is collected through questionnaires and secondary data is collected from research articles, journals, surveys, RBI reports, books, dissertations and internet. There are 221 bank employees are involved in the observation from both private and public sector banks. Stratified random sampling method was used to select samples for this study.

Job stress is measure by the scale prepared by Tate, Whatley &Clugston(1997), and the scale measured 4 aspects of stressors. They are role ambiguity, role conflict, work load and work family conflict. Organizational justice perception is measured with Magner, Johnson &Elfrink (1994) model which includes distributive justice and procedural justice. The organizational commitment was measured with shorten version of Porter et al (1974) scale. In order to measure the turnover intention of the employees, the items are adopted from Cummann et al, (1979). All the scales are presented in the questionnaire in which the respondents are asked to indicate their opinion to which they strongly disagree or strongly agree along a 5 point Likert scale.

6. Results

6.1 Background variables

The background information like gender, job cadre and type of bank are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Background variables

Background variables (N= 221)		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	168	76.0
	Female	53	24.0
Job cadre	Managers	119	53.8
	Non-managers	102	46.2
Type of bank	Public Sector	151	68.3
	Private Sector	70	31.7

The result from the table discloses that out of total 221 respondents 168 are males and remaining 53 are females are involved in the study. In ratio 76% are males and other remaining 24% are females. Job cadre is the second variable in background information which is used to determine the employee's position in their banks. The job cadre was analyzed by dividing into two groups as manager cadre and non-manager cadre. Result from the table reveals that out of total 53.8 are managers and 46.2 are non-managers. Another important background information is type of bank which the

respondents are belong. It is come to know from the table that 68.3% of the respondents are from public sector banks and remaining 31.7 % of them are from private sector banks.

6.2. Correlations

Correlation analysis is adopted to test the degree of relationship among the study variables. Table 2 is showing the correlation analysis.

Table 2. Correlation analysis

		Turnover intention	Job Stress	Organizational Justice	Organizational Commitment
Turnover intention	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	221			
Job Stress	Pearson Correlation	.302**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
	N	221	221		
Organizational Justice	Pearson Correlation	-.348**	-.558**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		

	N	221	221	221	
Organizational Commitment	Pearson Correlation	-.404**	-.625**	.522**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	221	221	221	221

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the table job stress is positively related to turnover intention with $r = .302$ and the significance value is less than 0.001. The results also show that organizational justice is negatively related the turnover intention with the correlation coefficient of $r = -.348$, which is significant at $p < .001$. It is further reveals that organizational commitment appears to be negatively correlated with turnover intention as $r = -.404$, $p < .001$.

6.3. Regression

Regression analysis was used to assess the influence of independent variables on dependent variable. The independent variables like job stress, organizational justice and organizational commitment were tested in the prediction of the dependent variable turnover intentions.

Table 3. Regression Analysis

Predictors	Turnover intentions		
	β	R^2	p value
Job stress	.304	.091	.000
Organizational justice	-.375	.121	.000
organizational commitment	-.489	.164	.000

From Table 3 it is clear that in the prediction turnover intention by the job stress is 9% with the value of R^2 is .091. In the estimation beta value is 0.304 at significance level of 0.000 ensured there is strong positive impact of job stress on turnover intentions. In second row the value of R^2 is .121 which shows that 12% variation made by organizational justice in turnover intentions. The beta coefficient = -.375 which is statistically significant at 1% level is established that there is significant negative influence made by the organizational justice on turnover intention. In third row the value of R^2 is .164 which shows that 16% variation in turnover intentions is predicted by organizational commitment and remaining by other factors. The beta value (-.489) is statistically significant by at 1% level. From the results it is found the organizational commitment is negatively predict the turnover intention.

reasons the productivity and smoother work flow of banks are disturbed and it also leads to turnover intention. The banks are need to take this issue seriously and invest much care on retaining their existing experienced employees. Because effective retention of the bank employees can increase the efficiency of the banks overall.

The findings of the study made a strong evidence on job stress has a significant positive influence on turnover intention. If the bank employees are facing high stress in their work place, they intend to leave their bank seriously. This findings is supported by Abang et al., (2009) as job stress is important indicator which can be linked with the employee's turnover negatively. The other two parameters like organizational justice and organizational commitment have significant positive impact on turnover intention. The study discourses important problem among employees in the banking sector in India with respect to bank employees' turnover. It was found that job stress, organizational justice, and organizational commitment were the main reasons of employees' turnover in Indian banking sector. This affords a high sensitive understanding of the context, turnover intentions, and to realize the importance of maintaining fair justice to the employees through that ensuring high employees' commitment towards their jobs.

7. Discussion and Conclusion

Turnover intention becomes a serious issue to all the organizations globally (Aamir, Khan, & Du, 2014). Employees are satisfied with their job autonomy and with their managers and the working condition as well. Employees' participation in one of the tool to make them happy to work with their current organizations (Khan & Anwar, 2012). But the results of this study make to understand that bank employees are not happy with their work due to stress in the job, justice practices by the banks and their commitment as well. Because of these

References

1. Aamir, M., Khan, S., & Du, J. (2014). An Empirical Study of Turnover Intentions in Call Centre Industry of Pakistan. *Journal of Human Resource and Sustainability Studies*, 2(December), 206–214.
2. Abang, A. M, May, C. L and Maw, K, L (2009): Human Resource Practices and Organisational Performance, Incentives as Moderator, *Journal of Academic Research in Economics*, Vol. 1 (2), pp 229-244.
3. Aryee, S., Budhwar, P.S., & Chen, Z.X. (2002). Trust as a mediator of the relationship between organizational justice and work outcomes: Test of a social exchange model. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 23, 267-285.
4. Cammann, C., Fichman, M., Jenkins, D. & Klesh, J. (1979). The Michigan Organizational Assessment Questionnaire. University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, Michigan.
5. Chrudden, H. J., & Sherman, A. W., (1972). Personal management, South-Western, Philippine.
6. Cohen-Charash, Y., & Spector, P.E. (2001). The role of justice in organizations: A meta-analysis. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 86, 278-324.

7. Dailey, R.C., & Kirk, D.J. (1992). Distributive and procedural justice as antecedents of job dissatisfaction and intent to turnover. *Human Relations*, 45, 305-317.
8. Earley, P.C., & Lind, E.A. (1987). Procedural justice and participation in task selection: The role of control in mediating justice judgments. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 52 (6), 1148-1160.
9. Firth L, David J Mellor, Kathleen A Moore, Claude Loquet (2007). How can managers reduce employee intention to quit?, *Journal of Management Psychology*. 19 (2): 170-187
10. Kevin, M. M., Joan. L. C., Adrian, J. W., (2004). Organizational change and employee turnover. *Personnel Review*. 33 (2):161-166.
11. Khan, A.S. and Anwar, F. (2012) An Exploratory Study of Appraisal Techniques from Pakistan Telecommunication Company Limited (PTCL). *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review* (OMAN Chapter), 7, 51-70. <http://dx.doi.org/10.12816/0002134>
12. Magner, N., Johnson, G.G., & Elfrink, J. (1994). Evidence on the relationship between procedural and distributive justice in performance appraisal and account faculty attitudes and performance. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 12, 325-341.
13. Meyer, J.P., & Allen, N.J. (1991). A three component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 1(1), 61-89.
14. Mowday, R.T., Steers, R.M., & Porter, L.W. (1979). The measurement of organizational commitment. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 14(2), 224-227.
15. Naumann, S.E., & Bennett, N. (2002). The effects of procedural justice climate on work group performance. *Small Group Research*, 33, 361-377.
16. Porter, L.W., Steers, R.M., Mowday, R.T. & Boulian, P.V. (1974). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover among psychiatric technicians. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59, 603-609.
17. Shukla, S., & Sinha, A. (2013). Employee Turnover in banking sector: Empirical evidence. *IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science*, 11(5), 57-61.
18. Tate, U., Whatley, A. & Clugston, M. (1997). Sources and outcomes of job tension: A three nation study. *International Journal of Management*, 3, 350-8.